

QUIZ**LAST NAME: WHITE****FIRST NAME: CAMILLE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What are the benefits of creating plans such as mind maps, outlines or storyboards for the prewriting planning stages?**
 - Plans allows the writer to think, trace and organized ideas for effective writing, giving clarity, coherence and cohesiveness.¹**
 - Plans allow flexibility to search for evidence, organize arguments and add supporting arguments or examples.²**
 - Write the topic sentence for the introduction then dissect the topic sentence into sub-topics.
 - Research and identify the topics with the most claims and begin writing about purpose followed by supportive statements.

¹ Linda D. Bloomberg and M. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2012), 21.

² Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Seventh Edition Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2007), 37, 67.

2. **What criterion are used to selecting a useful source for an academic essay?**

- The source must be primary or secondary, current published resource with a point of view that models your own research concepts and analysis.³**
- Sources are usually highly recommended books, magazines related to the topic.
- Use google search and blogs to search for latest reports that are simple and easy to read. These are classified as useful sources.
- Use encyclopedia and Wikipedia to research question as these are approved search databases.

3. **How would a literature review for qualitative study be assessed?**

- Features used in assessing a qualitative literature review include a defined purpose, description of skills and steps used in research, sources that identifies and analyzes claims of the developmental process of the research.⁴**
- A spreadsheet the most common ideas and claims of the subject would be recorded and all opposing views would be excluded.
- An evaluator will look for a creative insight which can be explained by a popular researcher in the field and look for continuous referrals to this study.
- Assessor would search for studies with relating to interviews of an opposing view in the literature review.

³ Turabian, 34.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 19.

4. **What are the types of questions a researcher should ask?**
- Conceptual questions are asked to understand the problems or issue.⁵**
 - Thesis statement is a question that is a broad question that answers the topic and problem statement identifies the process of the research
 - Practical question to fix a or improve a situation.⁵**
 - An applied question involves steps to better understand a problem.⁵**
5. **What is the importance of Turabian and what are its page formatting requirements?**
- Turabian is a writing style manual with two systems of referencing notes-bibliography and author date. Formatting involves body text of Times New Roman, indent of half inch of first line of each new paragraph, double space, right margin ragged and one space between sentences.⁶**
 - Turabian is a publishing style used by professionals. Formatting involves 11point Arial margins of 1 inch, double spacing between lines new paragraphs have no indents.
 - Turabian is a style used for data digital document. Formatting involves 11point Arial margins of one and a half inch, double spacing between lines and new paragraphs have indent of five spaces,
 - Turabian is a style used for institutions with manuscripts using only footnotes. Formatting involves 10-point Calibri margins of two inch, single spacing between lines new paragraphs have indent of five space.

⁵ Turabian, 18-19.

⁶ Turabian, 348-349.

6. **What is the purpose of WHO style guide?**

- WHO style guide is a reference manual preferred by professionals using WHO publishing. It provides cohesiveness and consistency in spelling, punctuation, terminology and formatting for authors and editors.**⁷
- WHO style guide is a go-to manual concentrated on scientific research using modern language.
- WHO style guide is a writing style for students and undergrads that is focused on documentation and citations.
- WHO style guide is a writing guide used in academic research for postgrad and undergrad students.

7. **What are the differences between a knowledge claim, and a Traditional Inquiry?**

- A knowledge claim is an assumption the researcher will learn based on ontology, epistemology, axiology, and methodology; a traditional inquiry is a post positive approach that has a specific direction for procedures in the research design.**⁸
- A knowledge claim is a researched quote with supportive examples and a traditional inquiry is an opposing view interview.
- A knowledge claim is a view that is valued based, while traditional inquiry is an approach based on policy.
- A knowledge claim is the interpretation and reflection of an issue and, a traditional inquiry is a famous statement based on observation.

8. **What are the differences between grounded theory and phenomenology?**

⁷World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 1 .

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 10.

- The researcher generates or discover a theory of process, action, or interaction grounded in the views of the research participants; phenomenology is the investigation of lived experience identifying the core essence of research participants.⁹**
 - It gives the coding process of each category
 - Using these theories behaviors can be distinguished by the population most frequent interest
 - Visual diagrams can be drawn to give process lows of each area.
9. **What is the advantage of using a conceptual framework in qualitative research approach?**
- A conceptual framework is a working tool that illustrates the application or construction of the research by framing the problem, purpose and how data is to be collected.¹⁰**
 - The design can display a long-term relationship with a variable as part of the whole population.
 - It displays characteristics of the population such as distribution, sample size and responding and non-responding populations.
 - The hypothesis can be related to statistical analysis of any variable.
10. **Why is description of findings and data results important in the interpretation of results?**

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 11.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 58.

- In the interpretation of results description provide evidence, logic, linkages of the research data provide a point of inference or educated guess.¹¹**
- The claims and problems are identified with a political group and related to history and culture
- Experts believe the views are controlled naturally in this section and displays an unchangeable variable.
- Literature is used together with data to suppressing problems within the research.

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¹¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 132.